

Rotor-Force Controller for Multirotors Under Aerodynamic Interferences

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Abstract

The use of multirotors for inspection tasks requires the ability to perform high-precision flights close to the environment, where aerodynamic effects appear and make control of the platform difficult. This paper presents a control solution for multirotors to deal with aerodynamic effects and other disturbances produced at a motor level. It combines the inclusion of a mechatronic system embedded in the multirotor power plant and a new control architecture focused on enabling a Rotor-Force Controller (RFC) at a motor level. Unlike model-based solutions developed in recent years, our solution can be used with any type of motor perturbation, such as ground and ceiling aerodynamic effects, wind effects, battery discharge and rotor damage effects. The implementation of both parts, the mechatronics system and the Rotor-Force Controller, are presented in this paper and experimentally validated in a custom testbench. The experiment shows that the proposed Rotor-Force Controller reduces the impact of aerodynamic effects on platform attitude approximately 80% compared with the results without the Rotor-Force Controller ¹.

Keywords: Multirotors, Aerodynamic Effects, Aerial Robotic Manipulators, Rotor-Force Controller

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¹Video of the paper: <https://youtu.be/eh8nuAPpAoA>

1. Introduction

Aerial manipulators combine the versatility and agility of aerial platforms with the capabilities of robotic manipulators [1, 2]. These have attracted a lot of interest in the last decade due to the wide spectrum of applications, ranging from inspection tasks [3, 4, 5] to support in post-disaster situations [6, 7, 8], and their societal benefits evidence that it is well worth the price of developing such technology. Nevertheless, the accuracy and reliability requirements for these unmanned vehicles are a major challenge for today's scientific community.

The challenges to be met in deploying such technology on a day-to-day basis extend to the entire chain of systems that typically make up an autonomous vehicle. These consist of developing robust guidance, navigation and control algorithms [9], accurate localization techniques [10] and useful human-machine interfaces, among others. This paper is driven by the imperative requirement encountered by most aerial manipulators to improve the levels of precision and safety during flight operations near objects [11]. In such environments, multirotors are susceptible to multiple aerodynamic disturbances due to the presence of non-linear and intricately challenging-to-model obstacles in their vicinity.

There are several state-of-the-art solutions focused on addressing the problem of flying under the influence of aerodynamic effects. These effects typically changes the thrust developed by the propeller for a commanded PWM by the autopilot. The best known of these effects in helicopter theory is the ground effect [12]. One type of solution is based on modelling the aerodynamic effect and incorporating that model into the control. In [13], the ground effect is modelled using the method of images, CFD simulations and experimental results. This ground effect model is then incorporated to the multirotor control. As the model depends on the distance between the propeller and the ground, it is measured using a 1D laser sensor. However, this type of solution loses generality because is limited to a model and uses an indirect observation. In this case, the model supposes that the propellers are parallel to the ground, and all are affected by the ground effect. Then, this solution does not represent other

situations as partial ground effect or other type of surfaces different from the ground (water, grass, ...). For example, in [14] the ceiling effect is modelled and incorporated into the control of the multicopter, which is used for the inspection of a bridge ceiling. This inspection has the same conditions of the model
35 identification: propellers parallel to the surface, all affected by the aerodynamic effect,... To summarize, this solution is not generalizable to other situations, as it requires modeling the specific situation [15, 16] for its incorporation into the control architecture [17].

Others type of solution for dealing with unmodeled disturbances is adaptive
40 control [18, 19, 20]. In [21] and [22], the authors propose an adaptive altitude controller that can deal with unknown parameters of a general ground effect model. This type of solution is more robust than the one presented above, as it is based on a general model and the robustness is guaranteed by the adaptive controller. However, the adaptive controller is only valid for the general ground
45 effect model proposed, and it can not deal with other situations not modelled as partial ground effect.

In [23], a Deep Learning Model Predictive Control is proposed to deal with the ground effect. The MPC has a nominal model which represents the free flight conditions of the platform, while the augmented ground effect model is
50 learned using deep learning. The proposed solution is more general than the model-based solution presented above. However, the augmented ground effect model estimated only the additional thrust of the platform due to the ground effect, while it does not consider additional torques that can appear when there is a partial ground effect.

55 As can be seen, most of the control solutions developed in the literature are based on models or estimate the influence of the aerodynamic effect as a total additional thrust in the platform. However, all aerodynamic effects affect at rotor-force level, and not at the level of the platform (body-level).

To overcome the limitations of previous works, this paper presents a Rotor-
60 Force Control (RFC) as an innovative control-mechanical solution to make the system aware of its actual actuation. This will accelerate the disturbance rejec-

tion produced in the propulsive system using onboard devices and avoid modelling errors. In other words, the proposed solution will increase the embodied intelligence of the robot by including information of the actual force generated
65 by the rotors in the control loop. The RFC directly targets to mitigate these effects in a general way by making the robot control aware of the force generated by sensing it through a mechanical system. As this solution is not model-based, it overcomes the limitations of the model-based solutions presented above. In particular, it outperforms model-based approaches when the disturbance can
70 be sensed at the rotor level. These are, for instance, the thrust increment due to ground effect or ceiling effect, the loss of performance when the propellers have physical defects, the disturbance generated by a cross-flow over thrust... In addition, this solution directly measures the motor thrust thanks to a force sensor. This allows to sense and correct the aerodynamic effects much faster
75 than other solutions, which estimate the additional thrust due to the aerodynamic effects using the dynamic model of the multirotor [13]. The closest to our work is [24], which applies an adaptive closed-loop speed control for brushless motors using the current measured by the ESCs. However, this solution controls the rotational speed of the rotors ω_R rather than the force exerted f_R
80 by them. Although both are usually related with the thrust coefficient C_T by the expression $f_R = C_T \omega_R^2$, under aerodynamic effects, this relation is no longer valid, and it is more appropriate to control the rotor force. Because of this, our work uses direct force observation without using any assumptions or neglecting un-modelled effects.

85 In summary, the main contribution of this work is the development of a Rotor-Force Controller (RFC) for multirotors, which guarantees that the force commanded to each motor by the allocation matrix is achieved. Our solution is specifically designed for multirotors performing inspection and maintenance tasks. These tasks require precise, close-proximity flight to the environment,
90 where aerodynamic interferences commonly occur, disturbing the platform's flight. The RFC has been experimentally validated on a customised testbench inducing independent or combined aerodynamic effects. The two innovations

needed to enable our force-aware controller in a standard multirotor are:

- Design a mechanical solution to install a force sensor on a rotor, necessary
95 to measure the exerted force.
- Adaptation of the standard control laws of a commercial autopilot to im-
plement the control of the rotor force.

This work validates the proposed solution using a custom testbench that
simulates the roll attitude of a multirotor. The testbench has a mobile platform
100 to test the behaviour of the Rotor-Force Controller under different aerodynamic
disturbances: ground effect, ceiling effect and ground and ceiling effect. Al-
though the proposed solution could be extended for all types of motor level
disturbances (defects on the propellers, defects on the motor, ...), this paper
focuses on its use for aerodynamic effects to keep the paper simplicity.

105 The rest of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 presents in detail
the Rotor-Force Controller for aerial manipulation, including the force sensor,
the new control structure of the autopilot and a theoretical analysis of the
superiority of this method over the standard architecture without RFC. Section
3 describes the implementation of the proposed Rotor-Force Controller to extend
110 the capabilities of a well-known commercial autopilot. The experimental results
are presented in Section 4. Finally, the conclusions of this work are summarized
in Section 5.

2. The Rotor-Force Controller in Multirotors.

2.1. Motivation

115 Multirotor dynamics is classically formulated considering a fixed world frame
 $\{W\} = \{X_W Y_W Z_W\}$ and a body frame $\{B\} = \{X_B Y_B Z_B\}$ attached to the
Center of Gravity (CoG) of the aerial platform. The multirotor state $\xi =$
 $[\mathbf{p} \ \boldsymbol{\eta}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is composed of the position and orientation of $\{B\}$ with respect
to $\{E\}$. The position of the centre of gravity of the aerial platform is described
120 by $\mathbf{p} = [x, y, z] \in \mathbb{R}^3$, expressed in $\{E\}$, while $\boldsymbol{\eta} = [\phi, \theta, \psi] \in \mathbb{R}^3$ includes the

Euler angles of the attitude of the aerial platform. Figure 1 shows these vectors, frames and the motor numeration of a quadrotor with ”+” configuration. According to the Euler-Lagrange formulation, the dynamic model of a standard UAV can be expressed in the usual matrix [13] form as:

$$\mathbf{M}(\xi)\ddot{\xi} + \mathbf{C}(\xi, \dot{\xi}) + \mathbf{G}(\xi) = \mathbf{R}\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{C}}(\omega_i) + \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{Ext}}, \quad (1)$$

125 where $\mathbf{M}(\xi) \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6}$ is the inertia matrix, $\mathbf{C}(\xi, \dot{\xi}) \in \mathbb{R}^6$ represents the centrifugal and Coriolis terms, whereas $\mathbf{G}(\xi) \in \mathbb{R}^6$ includes the gravitational forces. Then, $\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{C}} = [0 \ 0 \ T \ \tau_x \ \tau_y \ \tau_z]^T \in \mathbb{R}^6$ and $\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{Ext}} \in \mathbb{R}^6$ include the total thrust T and torques τ_x, τ_y, τ_z generated by the propellers, and the external forces and torques, such as those produced by the contact with the environment or the
 130 body drag among others. Finally, $\mathbf{R} = [\mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{WB}} \ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3}; \ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \ \mathbf{I}_{3 \times 3}] \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6}$ incorporates the rotation matrix $\mathbf{R}_{\mathbf{WB}} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ which allows to express the control vector $\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{C}}$ from the body frame into the world frame.

Figure 1: Frames, vectors and rotors enumeration.

Most of the previous works consider the actuation vector $\mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{C}} = \mathbf{F}_{\mathbf{C}}(\omega_i)$ as a function of the spin velocity of the propellers ω_i , where $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ and N is the
 135 number of motors. For example, without considering the aerodynamic effects, the mapping matrix of a quadrotor with ”+” configuration can be expressed just in function of the force motor f_i as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} T \\ \tau_x \\ \tau_y \\ \tau_z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & L & 0 & -L \\ -L & 0 & L & 0 \\ C_M & -C_M & C_M & -C_M \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_1(\omega_1) \\ f_2(\omega_2) \\ f_3(\omega_3) \\ f_4(\omega_4) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where $C_M = C_D/C_T$ compares the drag factor C_D with the thrust factor C_T .

However, recent research [25, 13] has shown that, if the aerodynamic effects are considered, the actuation vector is also dependent on the state of the platform ξ , $\mathbf{F}_C = \mathbf{F}_C(\omega_i, \xi)$. More specifically, the actuation vector depends on the relative position of each motor with respect to the environment, since aerodynamic effects affect each motor. Considering the aerodynamic effects in the formulation, the dynamic model of the platform is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{M}(\xi)\ddot{\xi} + \mathbf{C}(\xi, \dot{\xi}) + \mathbf{G}(\xi) = \mathbf{R}\mathbf{F}_C(\omega_i, \xi_i) + \mathbf{F}_{\text{Ext}}, \quad (3)$$

where now the forces and torques generated by the propellers \mathbf{F}_C depends also on the state of the platform ξ .

The total thrust and torques are related to the force and torque of each motor, thanks to the mapping matrix. For the case of a coplanar multirotor in ”+” configuration and considering the aerodynamic effects, the mapping matrix would be rewritten as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} T \\ \tau_x \\ \tau_y \\ \tau_z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & L & 0 & -L \\ -L & 0 & L & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} f_1(\omega_1, \xi) \\ f_2(\omega_2, \xi) \\ f_3(\omega_3, \xi) \\ f_4(\omega_4, \xi) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & -1 & 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} d_1(\omega_1) \\ d_2(\omega_2) \\ d_3(\omega_3) \\ d_4(\omega_4) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

where $f_i(\omega_i, \xi)$ and $d_i(\omega_i)$ are the force and torque generated by the motor i , respectively, and L is the distance between the CoG (Center of Gravity) of the multirotor and the motor position. This formulation considers the aerodynamic effects because the force f_i depends on the state of the platform ξ with respect to the environment. We have assumed that the torque $d_i(\omega_i)$ maintains independent of the state of the platform ξ or the aerodynamic effect here is negligible.

Indeed, to the best of the authors' knowledge, the torque under aerodynamic effect has not been modelled previously with this purpose.

The thrust under the aerodynamic effect is usually modeled as $f_i = K_i^{AE}(\xi_i)C_T\omega_i^2$,
 160 where $K_i^{AE}(\xi)$ is a coefficient to take into account the aerodynamic effect on motor i and C_T is the thrust coefficient of the propeller. As the aerodynamic effects appear when the motor is close to the environment, the function $K_i^{AE}(\xi)$ is different for each motor, due to the different relative positions of the motors with respect to the environment. This coefficient represents the modification on
 165 the motor thrust due to aerodynamic effects f_i^{AE} , such as ground effect [13] or ceiling effect [25]. That is:

$$K_i^{AE} = \frac{f_i^{AE}}{f_i^{NAE}} = \frac{f_i^{AE}}{C_T\omega_i^2}. \quad (5)$$

Most of the multirotor controllers do not consider aerodynamic effects at all and solve the allocation problem by ignoring that close to obstacles $K_i^{AE} \neq 1$. To do so, they transform the force required in body frame \mathbf{F}_C in PWM signal
 170 using a model of the motor that does not consider any disturbance at a rotor level like aerodynamic or wind effects, i.e., the control action is done in an open-loop fashion. Then, using the inverse or pseudo-inverse of the mapping matrix, the force f_i is computed. Therefore, if there are disturbances that modify the force exerted by the motor, it does not start to act until errors in the attitude or
 175 position of the platform are detected. Other works as [25, 13] consider it including a model in the control loop to mitigate a specific aerodynamic disturbance. Nevertheless, those models are limited to a specific situation and suffer from a lack of generality. Moreover, they need to use external sensors to localize each rotor with respect to the environment and then calculate the force disturbance
 180 at a motor level using a model and indirect observations. This paper proposes a solution that includes the direct observation of the exerted force by each motor in the control loop. Consequently, the result is a generalized approach to the problem that does not depend on any hypothesis or case studies.

2.2. The Rotor-Force Controller

185 Our Rotor-Force Controller adds feedback at the force level, allowing us to detect disturbances earlier and, therefore, to correct them earlier than the standard solution. These disturbances can be of any type, but always at the motor level, such as asymmetries in the propeller, defects in the propellers, ground effect, ceiling effect, wall effect, lateral air streams affecting the propeller, 190 defects in the motor, etc. As this work is focused on control under aerodynamic effects, the solution proposed is validated under different aerodynamic effects. Figure 2 shows the scheme of the classical approach and the solution proposed in this work, where the mixer is the inverse of the mapping matrix, $f_{i,ref}$ is the force reference of the motor i and f_i the measured force of the motor i , with 195 $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ and N is the number of motors.

Figure 2: Comparison between the standard solution and the proposed solution

Thus, to implement the RFC, it is necessary to measure the force exerted by each motor and to implement the control algorithm in an autopilot, which receives the measured force. Section 2.2.1 presents the type of force sensor chosen, whereas Section 2.2.2 describes the parts of the RFC in a general autopilot.

200 2.2.1. The Force Sensor

The force sensor is a standard load cell that measures the force as an electrical signal. The principle of operation of all force sensors is the same: force

causes a change in length. By measuring this variation of the length, the force is determined. In this case, as the motor thrust has a defined direction, a cantilever force sensor is used. In order to explain the working principle of the cantilever force sensor, Figure 3 shows the force sensor as a cantilever beam subjected to a load F_M , representing the thrust of the motor.

Figure 3: Cantilever force sensor.

In a beam subjected to a vertical force F_M , as Figure 3 shows, the upper part is in compression and the lower part in tension. In addition, the part under tension will increase its length, while the part under compression will decrease its length. In order to measure this length variation, strain gauges are used. Force sensors measure this length variation to determine the force to which they are subjected. Using a Wheatstone bridge circuit, the length variation is measured, and therefore, the force is determined. Figure 3 also shows the strain gauges of the Wheatstone bridge installed in the beam.

Thus, as shown above, the output voltage is proportional to the applied force:

$$F_M \propto \Delta L \propto \Delta R_i \propto \Delta V_{out}. \quad (6)$$

As the voltage variations ΔV_{out} are very small, it is necessary to use an amplification phase to adapt ΔV_{out} to a larger order of magnitude. In order to use the force measured in the RFC, the analog signal must be converted to digital with ADC (Analog to Digital Converter). An identification of the system is necessary to convert the ADC value to a force value. Finally, the measured force is filtered to reduce the noise level of the signal using a digital filter for

that.

225 In the previous analysis, the sensor has been considered in a static equilibrium. Although the sensor moves due to the movement of the platform, it can be shown that the inertia force is negligible compared to the motor force, so the analysis in static equilibrium is valid. The force equilibrium on the sensor is $m_{FS}a_{FS} = F_M + F_R$, where a_{FS} is the acceleration of the force sensor, F_M 230 the motor force and F_R is the reaction force on the sensor due to its connection with the quadrotor frame. To consider the static equilibrium for the analysis, the motor force must satisfy:

$$F_M \gg m_{FS}a_{FS}, \quad (7)$$

so $|F_M| \approx |F_R|$ and the static analysis is valid. Since the RFC is designed for multirotors in inspection tasks, condition (7) is satisfied, as these tasks typically 235 require slow movements with low angular accelerations. Furthermore, Section 3 numerically demonstrates condition (7).

2.2.2. Control architecture of Force-Awareness control

In order to exploit the RFC, the control architecture must be force-aware. Since no commercial autopilot is force-aware, it is necessary to modify the control 240 structure in order to use RFC. The RFC enables a close-loop control at force level allowing a faster response to possible disturbances in the force exerted by the motor. This controller takes place after the application of the allocation matrix and ensures each rotor is exerting its required force. Figure 4 shows the general controller of a multirotor, which is composed of a position controller, an attitude controller and the mixer. Typically, most of the autopilots use a PID 245 cascade for each controller. However, more advanced controllers can be used to generate the necessary wrench \mathbf{F}_C . After the mixer, the motor force $f_{i,ref}$ is converted to PWM signal using the quadratic model of the motor in an open loop fashion. However, our solution combines this model with a closed loop to regulate the disturbances. The RFC is composed of a feedforward compensator, 250 that is, the quadratic model, and a feedback compensator.

Figure 4: General controller of a multirotor, including the standard and our solution for computing the PWM.

The feedforward compensator of the RFC allows to respond quickly to changes in the force reference by changing the PWM output. However, this compensator has no information about possible disturbances that may affect the output. To overcome this problem, the feedback compensator is added, which corrects the PWM output of the feedforward compensator if differences between the real motor thrust and its reference are detected. In this way, this controller allows having more accurate control of the thrust in case of possible disturbances. A PID has been chosen for the feedback compensator as it has a simple implementation and low computational cost, allowing it to be used at a high frequency. Both compensators have to be implemented in an autopilot to convert it into a force-awareness autopilot.

2.3. Theoretical Control Performance Analysis

To justify the advantages of using RFC for disturbance suppression, we have examined the characteristic time of each control loop within each architectural configuration. In the standard control architecture, the lowest control loop is the attitude controller. Experimentally, this control loop is usually tuned to

have a first-order response in closed-loop, with a time constant in the range of $\tau_{ATT} \in [0.1, 0.3]$ s. In this case, the aerodynamic disturbance is observed as an error in the angle controller.

In the proposed RFC architecture, the lowest control loop is the Rotor-Force Controller. In this case, the aerodynamic disturbance is observed as an error in the force controller. As we present in Section 4, we were able to tune the controller to have a first-order response with a time constant of $\tau_{RFC} = 5.2$ ms.

Comparing both time constants we observe that $\tau_{ATT} \gg \tau_{RFC}$, which shows that the new control loop significantly reduces the response time to disturbances. Due to the lower time constant of the RFC, the disturbances like the aerodynamic effects can be rejected better than without the RFC, as we are observing and acting at a lower and faster loop, that is, the rotor-force level. To show the control improvement reached by this reduction in the response time, we can compare both cases, with RFC and without RFC, under a disturbance. Based on the results of our previous study, see Figure 27 of [13], we assume a first-order response in the angular dynamics ($\phi(t) = A_\phi(1 - e^{-t/\tau_{ATT}})$) against a rotor-force aerodynamic disturbance. The attitude controller would reject the aerodynamic disturbance approximately in a time of the order of its time constant τ_{ATT} , so the roll error would be $\phi_{ATT} \approx \phi(\tau_{ATT}) = A_\phi(1 - e^{-\tau_{ATT}/\tau_{ATT}})$. When the Rotor-Force Controller is added, the disturbance is rejected now in the RFC time constant τ_{RFC} , so the amplitude of the angle error remains $\phi_{RFC} = \phi(\tau_{RFC}) = A_\phi(1 - e^{-\tau_{RFC}/\tau_{ATT}})$. Comparing both disturbance amplitudes, the performance of the RFC η_{RFC} remains:

$$\eta_{RFC} = 100 \cdot \frac{\phi_{ATT} - \phi_{RFC}}{\phi_{ATT}} \in [91.9, 97.2] \%, \quad (8)$$

where we took into account the interval values of τ_{ATT} and the obtained value τ_{RFC} presented before. This result shows the improvement that can be achieved due to the RFC, as the disturbance is sensed before in the rotor-force control loop.

295 **3. Implementation**

After having presented the parts of the RFC in a general case, this section presents its implementation in a real case. Section 3.1 presents the design of the testbench to validate the RFC, Section 3.2 presents the integration of the force sensor in a commercial motor, whereas Section 3.3 presents the modification of
300 a commercial autopilot to make it force-aware.

3.1. Testbench

In order to validate the Rotor-Force Controller, a test bench has been designed and built. The objective of this testbench is to replicate the attitude behaviour of a multirotor. To do this, the testbench is composed of an external structure, a rotating structure and a mobile platform, as Figure 5 shows. The external structure is fixed and houses the rest of the components. In addition,
305 a protection grid has been added to the external structure in order to protect against possible accidents with the propellers.

Figure 5: Design of the testbench to validate the RFC.

The rotating structure is installed inside the external structure and simulates the roll rotation of a multirotor thanks to its axis bearings. The testbench
310 allows testing the RFC in two different configurations: with 0DoF (Degree of

Figure 6: Testbench mounted to validate the RFC.

Freedom), i.e. with the motor embedded, and with 1DoF, i.e. with the roll rotation of the multirotor. The 0DoF configuration is obtained by adding a locking bar to prevent rotation of the axis, as shown in Figure 7. First, thanks
 315 to the 0DoF configuration, the RFC is designed and implemented, as the only variable controlled is the force of the motor. This configuration allows testing and adjusting the RFC. Also, thanks to 0DoF configuration, it is possible to identify the model of the force sensor, i.e. the relationship between measuring voltage and applied force. Then, once the RFC is adjusted, the 1DoF configuration
 320 allows for validating the integration of the RFC in the attitude control since the roll angle is a free join.

The mobile platform allows the simulation of different flight situations under aerodynamic effects. It is mounted on two rails that allow it to slide along one axis. Its movement allows the introduction of the platform in the test bench to
 325 generate aerodynamic interference in a motor. The aerodynamic interferences that can be generated are the Ground Effect (GE), Ceiling Effect (CE) and Ground and Ceiling Effect (GCE). Thanks to it, the RFC can be evaluated under different aerodynamic situations. Figure 8 shows the mobile platform generating different aerodynamic effects.

Figure 7: Detailed view of the motor in the testbench with the 0DoF configuration.

3.2. Force Sensor Integration

The force sensor selected is the Strain Gauge Load Cell of Adafruit, which can measure up to 1 kg of force. The motorization selected is composed of the rotors DJI 2312E rotors, the DJI 9×4.5 propellers and the XRotor 40A ESCs. The maximal force of this motorization is 1 kg using a 4S LiPo battery, so the force sensor selected can be used.

To install the motor on the force sensor, two 3D parts have been designed and printed in ABS (Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene). As Figure 9 shows, the part A is directly screwed to the end of the force sensor and contains three through holes for attaching the part B. Then, part B is attached directly to the motor using four screws. Later, parts A and B are connected by three screws, joining the motor to the end of the force sensor. Finally, as Figure 9 shows, the motor is installed at the end of the sensor.

With the selected components, we can prove that the static analysis is satisfied using Equation (7). The mass of the rotating structure is $m_{RS} = 1 \text{ kg}$, and the sensor mass is $m_{FS} = 0.05 \text{ kg}$. The motor force F_M can be estimated as the required to keep the rotating structure in hover, and the sensor acceleration a_{FS} can be considered as the 10% of the gravity g , if the movements of the platform are considered to be slow, which occurs in inspection tasks. This value $a_{FS} \approx 10\%g$ is obtained taking into account the angular acceleration

Figure 8: Situations simulated by the mobile platform: a) No aerodynamic effect, b) Ground Effect (GE), c) Ceiling Effect (CE), d) Ground and Ceiling Effect (GCE).

Figure 9: Views of the motor with the force sensor and the 3D printed parts for the assembly.

350 limits $\ddot{\phi}(t) \in [-\ddot{\phi}_{Max}, \ddot{\phi}_{Max}]$ imposed by the controllers. In inspection tasks, the movements are slow, so we considered $\ddot{\phi}_{Max} = 1 \text{ rad/s}^2$ as it is the default value in *Ardupilot*. The maximal sensor acceleration can be estimated as $a_{FS}^{Max} \approx L\ddot{\phi}_{Max}$, where L is the distance between the multirotor center and the motor position, which is considered equal to that of the sensor. As the RFC

355 is a generic solution for multirotors, we consider the worst case $L_{Max} = 1 \text{ m}$, as is the case for some large aerial robots used for inspection in refineries [26]. In this case, we obtain $a_{FS}^{Max} \approx L\ddot{\phi}_{Max} = 1 \text{ m} \cdot 1 \text{ rad/s}^2 = 1 \text{ m/s}^2 \approx 10\%g$.

Considering these values, the forces are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F_M &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot 1 \text{ kg} \cdot 9.8 \text{ m/s}^2 = 4.9 \text{ N}, \\
 m_{FS} a_{FS} &= 0.05 \text{ kg} \cdot 0.10 \cdot 9.8 \text{ m/s}^2 = 0.049 \text{ N},
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{9}$$

which probe condition (7) and validates the static analysis.

360 Then, as the voltage output of the force sensor is very small, an amplification stage is necessary. For this purpose, the INA125PA instrumentation amplifier is used. This amplified signal is measured by an *Arduino Nano*, which converts it to a digital signal thanks to its ADC (Analog to Digital Converter). The noise level of the signal is analysed using the FFT (Fast Fourier Transform), which
 365 shows a uniform frequency spectrum corresponding to white noise. We use a Simple Moving Average (SMA) filter to filter the noise. This type of filter is used for smoothing the signal from short-term overshoots or noisy fluctuations and helps in retaining the true signal representation or retaining sharp step response. For this filter, we adjust the window size manually, in order to filter
 370 the signal but without inducing a significant time-delay in the measure. We choose $N_{WS} = 5$, where N_{WS} is the number of samples used in the window.

Finally, it is necessary to identify the relation between the ADC value and the force value. For that, an identification of the force sensor has been done. Figure 10 shows the ADC values obtained for different forces applied to the
 375 force sensor. The force of Figure 10 is normalized with the maximal force of the motor ($F_{max} = 1 \text{ kg}$). These points can be interpolated in order to obtain a cubic model of the sensor. The parameters that characterize our sensor are $C_0 = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-8}$, $C_1 = -2.38 \cdot 10^{-5}$, $C_2 = 9.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $C_3 = -1.36$.

3.3. RFC integration in Ardupilot

380 The RFC has been implemented in the open-source autopilot *Ardupilot*, which has been modified to add this new control loop. Likewise, the force is measured by a force sensor using an *Arduino Nano*. In order to receive the force measured by the *Arduino Nano*, the code of *Ardupilot* [27] has been modified. This communication is done through a serial port. The execution frequency of

Figure 10: System identification of the force sensor: ADC Value vs Force applied. The force is scaled by the maximum force of the motor ($F_{Max} = 1 \text{ kg}$).

385 the RFC is 400Hz, twice as fast as the attitude loop, which runs at 200Hz. In this way, disturbances in the motor thrust are detected earlier by RFC than by the attitude controller. This difference allows us to act sooner, so the effect on the platform attitude is lower with the RFC. Finally, the autopilot runs in a Raspberry Pi 3 Model B connected to the Emlid's sensors shield Navio2.

390 4. Results

In order to validate the Rotor-Force Controller, two types of experiments have been conducted. The first one consists of the 0DoF configuration, in which the motor is disturbed by inducing an aerodynamic effect. These first experiments allow us to adjust the PID parameters of the RFC. It also allows us to see the performance of the RFC on the motor thrust. These results are compared with the situation without RFC, in which the required force obtained by the

395

mixer is directly transformed in an open loop, as explained above. The second type of experiment is performed with the 1DoF configuration, where the motor is again working under aerodynamic effects. These experiments are carried
 400 out after having adjusted the RFC in the 0DoF configuration. In these experiments, it is possible to compare the improvement that the RFC introduces in the attitude of the multirotor under perturbations.

The aerodynamic effects induced in both experiments are ground effect, ceiling effect, and the combination of ground and ceiling effects at the same time. As
 405 presented in Section 3.1, this is possible by modifying only the mobile platform.

4.1. 0DoF Results

In the 0DoF configuration, there is no variation in the roll angle. Because of this, the most important magnitudes to compare are the force reference, the actual force ² and the PWM output. In this section, these magnitudes are used
 410 to evaluate the performance of the RFC. Furthermore, when the rotor is not under aerodynamic effect, it is represented with a green area (for example: OGE-Out of Ground Effect), while when it is under aerodynamic effect is represented with a red area (for example: IGE-In Ground Effect).

For the RFC we use a PI controller, as a fast response is needed, and the
 415 noise level of the signal makes difficult the estimation of the derivative term of the error. The gains are tuned using tuning rules similar to the ones presented in [28]. We tune the controller to have a first-order response in the closed-loop with a time constant of $\tau_{RFC} = 5.2 \text{ ms}$. Doing this, the controller gains remain $P_{RFC} = 4.1$, $I_{RFC} = 0.9$ and $D_{RFC} = 0.0$.

4.1.1. Ground Effect

In the Ground Effect (GE) experiments, the rotor is located at a distance of one rotor radius (1R) from the mobile platform. Figure 11a shows the results obtained in the experiment, where the motor has been subjected to the ground effect three times, first without the RFC and then with the RFC.

²All forces in the figures are scaled by the maximum force of the motor ($F_{Max} = 1 \text{ kg}$).

(a) Ground Effect.

(b) Ceiling Effect.

(c) Ground and Ceiling Effect.

Figure 11: Results with the 0DoF configuration.

425 When the RFC is not activated, i.e. the force computed by the mixer is
 converted to PWM signal in an open loop fashion, the ground effect disturbs
 the force exerted by the motor, exerting more force than requested. Likewise,
 without the RFC, the PWM remains constant regardless of whether there is
 ground effect or not. This is because the PWM output depends only on the
 430 force reference of the mixer, which is constant during the experiment. Therefore,
 since there is no force control, it cannot be guaranteed that the motor generates
 the force commanded by the mixer, as it happens in Figure 11a.

However, when the RFC is activated, an improvement in these aspects is
 observed, as the force control loop is closed thanks to the force sensor. When

435 the motor is subjected to the ground effect, the force exerted is quickly corrected,
and only a small variation is detected, as shown in Figure 11a. Likewise, the
PWM output varies when the RFC is activated. This is due to the fact that
it is modified to follow the force reference. In addition, it is observed that the
PWM required to exert the reference force when there is ground effect is lower
440 than when there is no aerodynamic effect. This is due to the fact that the
ground effect increases the thrust created by the motor for a speed. So, under
a ground effect, a lower rotational speed is needed for the same force without
aerodynamic effects.

4.1.2. *Ceiling Effect*

445 In the Ceiling Effect (CE) experiments, the rotor is located at 0.1R below
the mobile platform. In this case, it was possible to evaluate the performance
at such a small distance because there was no interference between the moving
platform and the rotating platform. Figure 11b shows the results obtained in
the experiments, where the motor has been subjected to the ceiling effect three
450 times, first without the RFC and then with the RFC.

In this case, the force increase due to the ceiling effect is greater than with
ground effect. Nevertheless, when the RFC is activated, the force is controlled
with only small disturbances being noticeable at the beginning and end of the
ceiling effect. Likewise, Figure 11b also shows how the RFC modifies the PWM
455 output to control the rotor force.

4.1.3. *Ground and Ceiling Effect*

In the Ground and Ceiling Effect (GCE) experiments, the rotor is located at
0.3R below the upper mobile platform and 1R above the lower mobile platform.
Figure 11c shows the results of the experiments, where the rotor has been sub-
460 jected to the aerodynamic effect three times, first without RFC and then with
RFC.

The results of this experiment are similar to those obtained previously. With-
out the RFC, the system is not able to follow the force reference, as it has no

feedback and does not modify the PWM output. When the RFC is activated,
 465 the controller is able to observe disturbances in the motor force and act on the
 PWM output to follow the force reference.

Finally, it can be concluded that the RFC allows the control of the reference
 force properly. The experiments also show that the RFC is able to mitigate
 different disturbances in an agnostic way.

470 4.2. 1DoF Results

Once the results with the 0DoF configuration have been discussed, the results
 of the 1DoF configuration are presented. In this configuration, a new motor is
 added to control the roll angle. This new motor is not disturbed by the mobile
 platform. In the 1DoF configuration, there is a new DoF and new variables are
 475 included in the analysis. The new variables that are included in the analyses are
 the roll angle and its reference and the rate angle and its reference. In addition,
 the force reference commanded by the mixer, the reference and the PWM of
 both motors are included as above.

As done before, when the rotor is not under the aerodynamic effect, it is
 480 represented with a green area (OGE-Out Ground Effect), while when it is under
 the aerodynamic effect is represented with a red area (IGE-In Ground Effect).
 In total 10 experiments were performed for each aerodynamic effect and each
 controller (with RFC and without RFC), making a total of 60 tests. In addition,
 Table 1 presents the average value $\overline{e_{\phi,Max}}$ of the maximal roll error $e_{\phi,Max} =$
 485 $max(|\phi^{ref} - \phi|)$ of all the experiments for each aerodynamic effect with and
 without the RFC, and the standard deviation $e_{\phi,Max}^{SD}$ of this maximal roll error.
 It also shows the improvement $\eta_{RFC} = \frac{\overline{e_{\phi,Max}^{RFC}} - \overline{e_{\phi,Max}^{w/o RFC}}}{\overline{e_{\phi,Max}^{w/o RFC}}}$ achieved with the use of
 the RFC, including the theoretical performance estimation using Equation (8)
 taking into account the characteristic times obtained for each control-loop. Both
 490 index are not directly comparable as the theoretical one is for estimation and
 based on some assumptions regarding the aerodynamic response. However, the
 order of magnitude is comparable, demonstrating the benefits of our proposed
 controller.

Table 1: Average maximal roll error, standard deviation of the maximal roll error, and improvement (experimentally and theoretical estimations) for the different aerodynamic effects (AE).

AE	w/o RFC		w/ RFC		η_{RFC}	
	$\overline{e_{\phi,Max}}$	$e_{\phi,Max}^{SD}$	$\overline{e_{\phi,Max}}$	$e_{\phi,Max}^{SD}$	Exp.	Th.
GE	2.96°	0.43°	0.71°	0.04°	76%	96%
CE	4.16°	0.28°	0.68°	0.01°	84%	96%
GCE	4.86°	0.05°	0.97°	0.13°	80%	96%

We use the same attitude and rate controllers in both cases for comparing the improvement due to the RFC controller. These controllers are tuned for having a first-order response in the closed-loop with a time constant of $\tau_{ATT} = 0.24$ s. We follow the tuning rules presented in [28], obtaining $P_{ATT} = 4.5$ for the attitude controller and $P_{RT} = 0.07$, $I_{RT} = 0.07$ and $D_{RT} = 0.0036$ for the rate controller.

4.2.1. Ground Effect

As done in the 0DoF configuration with ground effect, the rotor is located at a distance of 1R from the moving platform. Figure 12a shows the results obtained without the RFC, while Figure 12b represents the results obtained with the RFC.

As it can be observed, if the RFC is not used, every time the ground effect is induced, the attitude of the multirotor is disturbed. Likewise, when the ground effect disappears, the attitude is also perturbed due to the change of conditions. Also, the perturbation is eventually corrected since the attitude controller modifies the reference of the rate controller, which modifies the force reference of each motor, as shown in Figure 12a. However, when using the RFC, the attitude of the multirotor is not so disturbed, and therefore, the variations in the rate reference are smaller. This results in smaller changes in the force reference, as shown in Figure 12b.

(a) Without RFC. (b) With RFC.

Figure 12: Results with Ground Effect in the 1DoF configuration.

In addition, without RFC, even if only one motor has been disturbed with
515 ground effect, the reference force is modified in both motors since the torque
applied to correct the angle is generated by the difference of thrusts, i.e., the
thrust of one motor is reduced and the thrust of the other is increased. Likewise,
it is observed that the reference force and the output PWM have a very similar
curve. This is because the conversion of the force reference commanded by the
520 mixer to PWM signal is done in an open-loop fashion. Therefore, since there
is no force control, it cannot be guaranteed that the motor generates the force
commanded by the mixer, as it happens in Figure 12a. However, when using
RFC, the disturbance in the motor force is detected quickly thanks to the force
closed loop, and can be corrected before it disturbs the roll angle. This causes
525 the roll angle to be a little perturbed, and therefore, the force reference has

minor changes. It is also observed how the PWM is reduced when there is ground effect for the same force reference. This is because the ground effect increases the thrust for the same PWM, and therefore, it requires a lower PWM to keep generating the same thrust. Likewise, when using RFC, the second motor always generates the same thrust without changing its PWM, as it is not affected by the ground effect.

4.2.2. Ceiling Effect

In this case, the moving platform has been placed at a distance of $0.5R$ above the motor. If it is placed closer, as in the 0DoF case, the propeller could hit the ceiling when it disturbs the motor. Figure 13a represents the results obtained without RFC, while Figure 13b represents the results with RFC.

(a) Without RFC. (b) With RFC.

Figure 13: Results with Ceiling Effect in the 1DoF configuration.

Without RFC the ceiling effect disturbs the attitude of the platform, causing an error in the roll angle. This angle error causes changes in the rate reference, which modifies the force reference of both motors. Likewise, when the RFC
540 is not used, it is observed that, although the roll error is corrected, the force demanded to the motor under aerodynamic effect is different from the reference force (see Figure 13a).

However, when the RFC is used, the attitude error is smaller. This is because the RFC detects errors in the force of the motor under the ceiling effect, allowing
545 a quick response before it significantly affects the attitude of the platform. Also, since only one motor is affected by the aerodynamic effect, only one motor's PWM is modified, as Figure 13b shows.

4.2.3. *Ground and Ceiling Effect*

In this case, the rotor is located $0.5R$ below the upper moving platform and
550 $1R$ above the lower moving platform. Figure 14a and 14b represent the results obtained with and without RFC, respectively.

These results are similar to the previous ones. Without RFC, the aerodynamic effect disturbs the roll angle, which causes changes in the rate references to correct them. A difference is observed between the force and the force reference on the motor under the aerodynamic effect. In contrast, when RFC is
555 used, the attitude is much less disturbed by aerodynamic effects since RFC is able to correct the force perturbations caused by the aerodynamic effect quickly. This can be seen in how the PWM of motor 1 is quickly modified to generate the reference force demanded by the mixer.

560 **5. Conclusion**

This paper has presented the design, control and experimental validation of a Rotor-Force Controller (RFC) for multirotors. It proposes the use of a force sensor to measure the thrust generated by the propellers combined with a new control architecture that enables the use of the RFC in a commercial autopilot.
565 The paper includes the mechatronic design for the force sensor integration and

Figure 14: Results with Ground and Ceiling Effect in the 1DoF configuration.

the modifications in a well-known autopilot solution (*Ardupilot*). The system has been validated in a custom testbench for different aerodynamic effects. The experiments show that the use of the RFC enables a faster reaction against thrust level disturbances. The experimental results also show that the RFC improves by up to 82% the attitude control, compared with the standard solution. As future works, we propose the inclusion of the RFC in a complete multirotor and its validation in real environments.

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